

A rapid analytical method for the determination of gold in geochemical materials by atomic absorption spectrophotometry

T. Venugopal^a, L. Giridharan^{a*}, C. Anbuselvan^b and J. Gandhiraj^c

^aDepartment of Geology and Mining, Thiru. Vi. Ka Industrial Estate, Guindy, Chennai-600 032, India

E-mail : girilogu@yahoo.com

^bPachaiyappa College, Chennai, India

^cR. K. M. Vivekananda College, Chennai, India

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An alternative method for fire-assay technique for the determination of gold in geochemical samples is described. In this method, the sample decomposition is effected by treating with a mixture of HCl and bleaching powder, followed by co-precipitation with tellurium and the precipitate is collected in benzene. Gold along with tellurium is then extracted in aqua regia and the noble metal is determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The method is simple, rapid and economic and found to be ideal for determination of gold in rock and other geochemical samples.

With the increasing demand for the low level determination of gold in geochemical materials such as rocks and placer samples a number of methods are available for the determination of gold. Out of these the fire-assay¹ is the most widely used and accepted procedure for gold analysis. Gold extraction and chemical pre-concentration are widely used for gold analysis²⁻⁵ since the distribution of noble metal in rocks is usually dispersed and in low concentration.

For low-level gold determination, numerous pre-concentration procedures have been reported and the preparation technique most frequently used is bromine/acid leach followed by an organic solvent extraction. However bromine vapours are very hazardous and difficult to handle in the laboratory. In the method described here instead of bromine/HCl^{6,8}, chlorine/HCl are used for the extraction of gold. Gold is co-precipitated with tellurium and the tellurium along with the noble metal is collected into an organic solvent. Gold is then re-extracted into aqua regia and determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The method provides an accurate and precise alternative to other methods for the determination of gold.

Results and discussion

Recovery of gold from known amounts of pure gold metal solution was found to be satisfactory by the proposed extraction procedure⁶. The efficiency of tellurium co-pre-

cipitation procedure is very much comparable with that of mercuric co-precipitation method⁷ (Table 1).

The gold contents of two international standards and four in-house standards are determined by the proposed extraction procedure, fire-assay procedure and by the bromine extraction technique and the results are presented in Table 2. Good agreement is observed between the proposed method and the internationally followed procedure.

Table 1. Comparison of mercuric co-precipitation and tellurium co-precipitation

Sample no.	Gold taken (µg)	Gold found (µg)	
		Mercuric co-precipitation	Tellurium co-precipitation
1	3.0	2.99	3.0
2	6.0	6.02	5.99
3	10.0	10.01	10.01
4	20.0	19.97	19.98
5	50.0	49.96	49.94

Table 2. Comparison of results obtained using fire-assay, bromine extraction technique and the proposed method

Sample no.	Certified gold content (µg/g)	Value obtained (µg g ⁻¹)		
		Fire-assay	Bromine extraction technique	Proposed technique
PTMN-1	1.80	1.74	1.72	1.76
UTM-1	0.048	0.047	0.046	0.049
GV-1	4.50	4.44	4.41	4.49
GV-2	1.50	1.49	1.49	1.44
LN-3	3.70	3.68	3.65	3.72
LN-4	9.80	9.70	9.71	9.78

Eight individual gold determination for each of the two geochemical standards and two in-house standards were performed to evaluate the reproducibility of 10 g of sample weight. Good precisions were obtained for all samples and standards (Table 3).

Table 3. Reproducibility of values for 10 g of sample analyzed by the proposed method $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$

Serial no.	Samples			LN3	LN4
	A	B	C		
1	1.20	1.81	3.91	3.65	9.78
2	1.24	1.90	3.79	3.75	9.60
3	1.09	1.72	3.85	3.60	9.82
4	1.17	1.69	3.99	3.79	9.71
5	1.29	1.89	4.05	3.69	9.85
6	1.07	1.91	3.91	3.38	9.69
7	1.08	1.52	3.80	3.77	9.71
8	1.00	1.72	4.02	3.71	9.85
Mean	1.14	1.77	3.92	3.67	9.75
Standard deviation	0.098	0.134	0.099	0.132	0.083

It is known that gold dissolves in aqueous chloride solution to form both Au^{I} and Au^{III} chloride complex. The dissolution of gold occurs in two stages first the formation of Au^{I} chloride on the gold surface and then formation of AuCl_2^- . During the second stage this species in turn is either diffused into the solution as AuCl_2^- or oxidized to form AuCl_4^- . This process needs very strong oxidizing condition for gold dissolution. Gold dissolves extremely fast under acidic condition and when Au-species are compared, the Au^{III} complex is expected to be more stable in Au-HCl- H_2O system.

(E^0 is the standard reduction potential)

From the above equation it is clear that the oxidation of Au to Au^{I} and Au^{III} requires strong oxidation potential. In our present investigation bleaching powder in hydrochloric acid plays the role of strong oxidizing agent. In aqueous medium bleaching powder releases chloride ions which attacks the gold in its native form in geochemical soil samples.

Gold in Au^{I} and Au^{III} states form complexes viz. HAuCl_2 and HAuCl_4 and goes into the solution leaving behind silica which is almost always present in high proportion in geochemical rock and solid sample. Hence the inter-

ference from silica in the determination is removed. The other major interfering radicals namely iron, calcium, magnesium etc., are also removed from the solution by selectively co-precipitating gold with the tellurium. At this stage only gold and platinum group of elements gets precipitated along with tellurium leaving behind all other interfering matrix elements in the analysis.

Taking the analytical accuracy of the proposed method into account, it is clear that almost all gold contents in international as well as in-house standards were recovered and estimated and hence the method is found to be consistent for the analysis of gold.

Experimental

A GBC-902 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC Scientific Equipment) was used for determination of gold. Instrumental setting used were : wave length 242.8 nm, lamp current 4.0 mA, slit width 0.5 nm, air/acetylene 4 : 1 and burner head 3.5 cm. HCl and HNO_3 used are of A.R. grade (AnalaR grade, Merck), calcium chlorohypochlorite (Bleaching powder) (L.R. grade); all other reagents used are of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of tellurium solution (1 mg/ml in 10% HCl) : 1.24 g of TeO_2 are dissolved in 30 ml of aqua regia and remaining nitric acid is removed by two successive evaporation with HCl. 100 ml of HCl is added and made up to 1 litre with de-ionized water.

Preparation of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ standard : Dissolve 1.0000 g of gold in 20 ml of aqua regia (5 ml conc. nitric acid and 15 ml conc. hydrochloric acid) and dilute to 1 litre to obtain 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Au.

Finely ground samples of 100-mesh size is dried at 650°C in a muffle furnace and cooled in a desiccator. 10 g of this sample is accurately weighed and transformed to a 250 ml beaker. 7.5 g of calcium hypochlorite (bleaching powder) is added and thoroughly mixed with a glass rod. To this, 50 ml of conc. HCl is added slowly with constant stirring and heated gently on a hot plate at about 140°C for about four hours for complete digestion. 20 ml of 6 N HCl is added at an interval of 1 h. The beaker is removed from the hot plate; the solution is filtered through Whatman 40 filter paper and the residue is washed twice with 6 N HCl. The solution is diluted to about 60 ml and heated on a hot plate at about 80°C . 5 ml of tellurium solution is added followed by drop wise addition of Sn^{II} chloride solution until black tellurium and gold metals are precipitated. A further 1 ml of Sn^{II} chloride solution is added and a beaker is heated on a hot plate at low heat without actually boiling to facilitate coagulation of tellurium precipitate. The beaker is al-

lowed to cool at room temperature and the contents are then transferred into a 250 ml separating flask containing 5 ml of benzene. The contents are shaken for 30 s. The tellurium precipitate collects in the organic layer. The lower aqueous layer is discarded and the organic layer is rinsed with two portions of 10% ammonium chloride solution. To the organic layer, 2.5 ml aqua regia is added and after shaking the aqueous layer containing dissolved tellurium and gold is collected in graduated tube. The benzene layer is rinsed with 2 ml of deionized water and the washings are collected in the same test tube containing the aqueous extract. The solution after adjusting the volume to 5 ml with deionized water is then fed into AAS instrument and the content of Au is determined.

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